

Training Workshop

Deliverable D3.1

31 December 2024

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document details

Project Acronym/Name:	ORION
Project URL:	https://he-orion.eu/
Project Type:	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
EU CALL:	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-03
Grant Agreement No.:	101158432
Project Start Date:	01/09/24
Project End Date:	01/09/27
Work package:	WP3
Deliverable:	D3.1 Training Workshop
Due date of Deliverable:	31/12/24
Actual Submission Date:	24/01/25
Name of Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable:	AugmentCity
Reviewed by:	Fengshuo Hao & Zhiyu Pan : RWTH
Revision:	
Dissemination Level*:	PU

*PU=Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CI=Classified

Document History

Version	Date	Description	Author(s)
1.0	12/12/2024	First Draft	Scott Young (AugmentCity)
2.0	17/01/2024	Second Draft (incorporating comments)	Scott Young (AugmentCity)
3.0			
4.0			
5.0			

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© Partners of the Consortium, 2031

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Acknowledgements

This deliverable was developed based on collective efforts from all partners of the consortium.

Glossary and Abbreviations

DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
GDT	Graphical Digital Twin
VDT	Virgin Digital Twin

Table of Contents

- Executive Summary 7
- 1. Introduction 8
 - 1.1. About the project..... 8
 - 1.2. Objectives of D3.1..... 9
 - 1.3. Targets of D3.1 9
 - 1.4. Methodology 9
- 2. Training 11
 - 2.1. Webinar 1: General Introduction 11
 - 2.2. GDT Playground Scene..... 12
 - 2.3. Webinar 2: Technical Introduction..... 13
 - 2.4. GDT User Stories..... 14
 - 2.5. Survey 14
 - 3.1 Summary..... 16
 - 3.2 Limitations and weaknesses 16
- ANNEXES..... 18
 - A1: Webinar 1: Description, agenda & participants..... 18
 - A2: Webinar 2: Description, agenda & participants..... 20
 - B1: ORION GDT Story Template 22
 - C1: ORION: Survey 23
 - C2: ORION: Survey Results..... 24

List of Figures

Figure 1 : Project Organogram.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 2 : Three strands	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 3 : Timeframe of training	11
Figure 4: Screenshot of playground demo scene.....	12
Figure 5 : GDT User Story process.....	14
Figure 6 : GDT User Story Template.....	22

List of Tables

Table 1 : Webinar 1 Attendee's	19
Table 2 : Webinar 2 Attendees	21

Executive Summary

The Graphical Digital Twin (GDT) will serve as the primary platform to visualise the Use Case scenarios within the ORION project. Therefore, training on the GDT is essential to ensure that all partners understand its current capabilities and future potential when developing their own Use Case.

Under '**Task 3.5.1 Introduction to GDT**', it was envisaged to host a single introductory workshop at the UN Futurelab in Ålesund, home of AugmentCity between M1-M3. However, given the global nature of the ORION project with partners outside the EU, it was determined that moving it online would be more efficient and effective.

Building on previous experience from past EU Horizon Projects, AugmentCity understood that a single workshop, would only be able to impart a rudimentary knowledge of the GDT software. It was therefore essential to expand on this to embed any knowledge gained.

Consequently, 2 webinars were designed to educate Project Partners. In addition, a demonstration "**Playground**" scene was created to give partners the "hands-on" experience as required under **T3.5.1**. The aim was not only to increase partners' knowledge of the GDT but also to deepen the understanding of their own Use Case through a better understanding of the GDT capabilities.

Finally, a survey was issued to Partners to capture quantitatively and qualitatively their experience of the webinars, the demo "playground" scene and the GDT software itself, to better understand their experience and the level of training acquired by them.

1. Introduction

1.1. About the project

ORION is committed to advancing European leadership in science and technology by driving the twin energy transition for stakeholders across the energy value chain. Through a quintuple-helix model of collaboration, ORION provides a modular toolbox of digital breakthrough components, validated in hydro, solar, and wave energy operations across four continents. Central to ORION's vision (as shown in Figure 1) is the integration of these innovations into **human-centric Digital Twin applications, enabling the digitalisation of critical operational and business processes** within each Use Case. This seeks to increase the share of renewables in global electricity grids, reduce fossil fuel consumption, and address the challenges posed by rising energy demand, geopolitical uncertainty, and climate conditions. In collaboration with top research and innovation entities from eight countries across four continents, ORION will conduct high-impact testing and validation across five unique use cases. This will promote multidisciplinary knowledge, leading to the development of solutions that transform energy value chains globally.

Figure 1 : Project Organogram: showing GDT at top

1.2. Objectives of D3.1

This deliverable was developed in the context of **WP3**, which has the following objectives:

- ✓ **O3.1:** Develop ground-breaking algorithms and methodology based on sensor technologies to monitor health-status of the floating offshore wave energy converters.
- ✓ **O3.2:** Extend the standard model to include dynamic modelling and 3D representation.
- ✓ **O3.3:** Develop an effective optimisation tool to support the multiple stakeholder's decision making in RES and fossil fuels optimisation scenarios.
- ✓ **O3.4:** Develop an advanced digital information asset tool.
- ✓ **O3.5:** Develop the next generation human-centric Digital Twin applications.

1.3. Targets of D3.1

This deliverable's primary focus is to increase partners awareness, knowledge and understanding of AugmentCity's GDT as well as its current and future capabilities. Additionally, through this process it is hoped that the partners will then:

1. Better understand how their Use Case may benefit from the DT
2. Identify required data sources and formats for use in the GDT
3. Identify potential gaps in services/simulations for their Use Case
4. Make early requests for new functionalities in the GDT

1.4. Methodology

To meet the D3.1 targets the training comprises of 2 strands. These are:

- ✓ **Task 3.5.1 Introduction to Digital Twins:** A series of training webinars given to partners to introduce them to the concept of digital twins and the AugmentCity GDT platform.
- ✓ **GDT User Story:** The GDT user story is designed to focus the Use Cases on how they envisage the AugmentCity GDT software will ultimately be able to achieve for them at the project conclusion. It is an aspiration document that allows both the Use Case and AugmentCity to use as a target and to increase understanding of goals. It is a live document and will be refined over time as the project progresses.

Figure 2: Strands diagram

As the diagram above illustrates, the webinars are the starting point, increasing partners knowledge moving forward through the project whilst the GDT user story describes the ultimate end target as a reference to work backwards from, during the projects progress. The GDT demo scene is where the Use Cases have a “hands-on” experience where knowledge gained and GDT User Story project aspirations meet.

2. Training

As part of Task 3.5.1 Introduction to GDT (M1-M3) two webinars were organised to introduce and onboard the Orion partners to the GDT. The first webinar was designed as general introduction to the AugmentCity platform, and the second was focused on the more technical aspects of inputting and visualising different data sets within the twin.

Figure 3: Timeframe of training

2.1. Webinar 1: General Introduction

The first webinar was held on the **21st October 2024**. 25 people viewed the webinar invite, 21 registered and 22 attended (see annexe A1 for details on agenda and participants).

Hosted by WP4 lead Scott Young, the hour-long webinar was conducted by AugmentCity's Customer Success Manager; Stig Øveras and was intended as a general introduction to the AugmentCity GDT (Sandbox). It was assumed that those attending had no prior knowledge, and this introduction was designed to ensure that attendees felt comfortable in using the GDT. The webinar covered the following in detail:

- ✓ Logging into Sandbox
- ✓ Workspaces and scenes
- ✓ Help pages
- ✓ Opening a scene
- ✓ Navigation
- ✓ Scenarios
- ✓ Adding Objects
- ✓ Pin and comments tool
- ✓ Terrain display themes
- ✓ Weather settings
- ✓ Terrain editing

Unfortunately, due to technical issues the webinar failed to record, however AugmentCity resolved this issue by creating a separate training video that covered all aspects of the webinar and was issued to all those invited to the webinar. The training video can be viewed here:

<https://vimeo.com/1025109401/3a821bb375>

2.2. GDT Playground Scene

To ensure attendees from the first webinar could build on the knowledge gained, and have a **“hands-on” experience**, a demo GDT scene was created specifically for the ORION project. This scene was an exact copy of that demonstrated at the webinar. The term **“playground”** was used to describe this scene to instil a sense of curiosity and engagement for partners and to encourage them to play with the GDT, without fear of “breaking” anything. Moving forward in the project having a separate demo scene allows partners to experiment without fear of damaging their own use case scene in the future when they wish to experiment or introduce others within their team on the GDT potential.

Figure 3: Screenshot of playground demo scene

In the figure above can be seen a screenshot of the playground scene in action. Included within the scene are a variety of scenarios showing various data type visualizations. Any user logged into the playground scene is free to switch between these scenarios and familiarise themselves with the controls and interface as demonstrated at the first webinar. Access to the Playground demo scene was opened to the relevant partners on the **28th October 2024**

(M2), who were notified by email with instructions on how to download the relevant plugin software to run the GDT. Since the initial email has been issued, various Use Cases have asked for access to the GDT and the Playground demo to be expanded to include additional colleagues, which has been actioned.

2.3. Webinar 2: Technical Introduction

A second webinar was held on the **22nd November 2024 (M3)**, and was rescheduled from the previous week due to illness of the main presenter. The webinar was again hosted by WP4 lead Scott Young and this time presented by Dr Paul Halas, AugmentCity's Project Engineer / GIS data specialist.

This webinar focused on the more technical aspects of inputting and visualising data, both the topic and the requirement to reschedule this may explain the lower attendance rate; 13 viewed the webinar invite, 12 registered and 10 attended (see annexe A2 for details on agenda and participants).

The webinar recording can be found here : [**ORION 2nd AugmentCity Webinar Introduction to working with Data and the AC GDT**](#)

AugmentCity's Paul Halas presented a Virgin Digital Twin (VDT) of the playground scene to the webinar. A VDT is a GDT without data only terrain and buildings. From here Paul then recreated the Playground scene in full, showing how various data types can be imported, where the data is stored and how it can be visualised. The topics covered were:

- ✓ Road networks (i.e.show traffic/ road capacity & movement)
- ✓ Pins examples (locations of points of interest)
- ✓ Bargraph timeline (Point data over time for example energy usage)
- ✓ Heatmap timeline (area data over time ie microclimate changes)
- ✓ Map overlays (colouring of the 3D model based on values)
- ✓ Ribbons (showing linear data: i.e. energy grids)
- ✓ Building colours (static): (identification of building types)
- ✓ Building colours (timeline) : (i.e. building energy consumption over time)
- ✓ Lollipop : (KPI information for object or place)
- ✓ 3D objects : (importing of new 3d objects ie PV cells)

2.4. GDT User Stories

Figure 4 : GDT User Story process

AugmentCity have recently introduced a new procedure to increase understanding of the GDT end users needs and reduce abortive work. At the start of every project a “GDT User Story” template is issued to the end user. In this template, a series of aspirational questions are asked to help the end user describe a “story” of how they would want to use the GDT, including the information they would like to see within it and how they would use it in a real-world situation.

Documentation such as this proves invaluable in creating a benchmark to measure progress. From this GDT User Story document, a series of 2D visual mock-ups are created by AugmentCity for feedback from the end user to ensure that their aspirations have been interpreted correctly. The document also proves an invaluable reference for AugmentCity’s internal team of developers if a new feature is requested within the GDT User Story that is not yet currently available within the GDT tool.

The GDT User Story template was issued **7th October 2024** with a requested response date of **25th October 2024**. Currently of the 6 Use Cases, only Cape Verde, Ålesund, Brazil and Slovenia have responded, with Portugal and Canada still outstanding. It is a live document that will be refined as the project progresses.

2.5. Survey

An online survey was issued to all attendees of both webinars (37 in total), inviting feedback prior to the festive break. It contains 26 questions that gather data from the participant both on their prior knowledge and that gained from their training experience. Despite two subsequent emails requesting people to participate in the survey and the 32 people viewing it, only 16 started with 8 completing it. With an average completion time of 13mins. * **MERGEFORMAT**

Of the Use Cases, only Brazil and Cape Verde completed the survey see : **Figure 5: Survey Participants.**

Figure 5: Survey Participants

The survey can be located online here: [ORION TRAINING WORKSHOP SURVEY](#).
A detailed breakdown of the responses can be found in **annex C2: ORION: Survey Results**.

3. Conclusion

3.1 Summary

To conclude, both from the online survey and from direct feedback the training webinars were well received by the Partners. Having access to the GDT demo “Playground” scene was considered by partners to be the most beneficial element of the training and the requests to expand access to other colleagues scene should be viewed positively.

Responses to the survey question: **After the training webinars and ORION playground scene, do you have a clearer understanding on how you may benefit from using the GDT?**

- ✓ “I will not be working directly with GDT but my impression is that the GDT is a very good tool to display different scenarios in an understandably way for people with little or no technical experience.”
- ✓ “yes, it is very useful to know how GDT works”
- ✓ “with the training webinars and the ORION playground scenario gave me an idea of how to use the GDT, but my biggest problem is how to build a new scenario and enter it into the GDT. What’s the best file format?”
- ✓ “I think it will be very useful for use case 1 - Cape Verde”

3.2 Limitations and weaknesses

Key Findings

Organising the training workshops at the very start of the project allowed partners to quickly become familiar with the AugmentCity GDT and built momentum into the project. Separating the webinars into technical and non-technical also allowed a greater range and depth of knowledge to be exchanged and sped the onboarding process of partners as noted in the survey.

Weakneses

Organising dates for the training webinars and obtaining engagement from some partners has proved to be challenging, perhaps due to the varied time zone issues, which had a compound effect on project delivery.

Future training webinars should look to have dates locked into the calendar during consortium meetings so diaries can be agreed rapidly in person. (With hindsight these GDT training sessions should have been agreed at the Kick-off meeting) Additionally it should be considered whether these training sessions

are mandatory for all partners to ensure maximum participation and knowledge transfer.

Lastly, whilst online surveys can gather detailed knowledge, it is impossible to enforce engagement. An alternative would be to have a review meeting after both training webinars in which the same questions are asked in an interactive manner, using such tools as Mentimeter. This would allow greater cross pollination between Use Cases and partners and would be a recommendation for any future training sessions within and out with the project.

ANNEXES

A1: Webinar 1: Description, agenda & participants

AUGMENT CITY GDT DEMONSTRATION

ORION : Introduction to AugmentCity GDT webinar

Details

ORION : Welcome to this short introductory session of the AugmentCity GDT.

This webinar will be hosted by WP4 lead Scott Young and the demonstration itself will be given by AugmentCity's customer success manager; Stig Øverås.

In this session Stig will present the interface, controls & data visualization types with the GDT. There will be a short Q&A at the end in which any questions you may have can be raised. Please feel free to add you questions into the Q&A section during the talk.

After this session the partners will be given access to the ORION playground scene. A scene in which you can familiarise yourself with the interface and controls as demonstrated in todays webinar.

We look forward to you seeing you.

Scott

Agenda:

- 16:00 - 16:05 (CET) Welcome and introduction : Scott Young
- 16:05 - 16:50 (CET) AugmentCity Demonstration : Stig Øverås
- 16:50 - 17:00n (CET) Q&A's : Scott & Stig

Speakers (1)

Stig Øverås
Customer Success Manager
Augment City
Customer Success Manager

This event has passed.

Details

 Mon, Oct 21

 4:00 PM - 5:00 PM GMT+2

 Online event

[Register](#)

Figure 5: Webinar 1 invite to participants

#	Name	Role
1	Scott Young	Organiser
2	Stig Øverås	Presenter
3	Paul Halas	Attendee
4	Anja Diez	Attendee
5	António Varela	Attendee
6	Stine Wilhelmine Holm	Attendee
7	David Volk	Attendee
8	Sidnei Cruz	Attendee
9	Fengshuo Hao	Attendee
10	Eliot SOUTHON	Attendee
11	Tatiana Guedes	Attendee
12	Qing Zhao	Attendee
13	Zhiyu Pan	Attendee
14	José Neves	Attendee
15	Henrique Évora	Attendee
16	Hossam Afifi	Attendee
17	Jøran Mentzoni Eilertsen	Attendee
18	Robson Dias	Attendee
19	Matheus Custodio Machado	Attendee
20	Emanuel van Emmerik	Attendee
21	Rodrigo Gloria	Attendee
22	luan santos	Attendee

Table 1 : Webinar 1 Attendees

A2: Webinar 2: Description, agenda & participants

ORION : 2nd AugmentCity Webinar: Introduction to working with Data and the AC GDT

This event has passed.

Details

- Fri, Nov 22
- 4:00 PM - 5:00 PM GMT+1
- Online event

Register

Details

Following last weeks cancellation.

This is the rescheduled 2nd webinar.

This webinar will be hosted by WP4 lead Scott Young and the demonstration itself will be given by AugmentCity's GIS Project engineer / GIS data specialist Paul Halas.

This is the 2nd webinar for ORION to demonstrate the AugmentCity GDT and it will build up on the 1st that gave a general introduction . In this session Paul will focus on the more technical aspects; the type of data we use, how to import it into the GDT and how it can be visualised.

There will be a short Q&A at the end in which any questions you may have can be raised.

Please feel free to add you questions into the Q&A section during the talk.

We look forward to you seeing you.

Agenda:

- 16:00 - 16:05 (CET) Welcome and introduction : Scott Young
- 16:05 - 16:50 (CET) AugmentCity Technical Demonstration : Paul Halas
- 16:50 - 17:00 (CET) Q&A's : Scott & Paul

Figure 6: Webinar 1 invite to participants

#	Name	Role
1	Scott Young	Organiser
2	Paul Halas	Presenter
3	Anja Diez	Attendee
4	Sidnei Cruz	Attendee
5	António Varela	Attendee
6	Stine Wilhelmine Holm	Attendee
7	David Volk	Attendee
8	Eliot SOUTHON	Attendee
9	Shannon Truloff	Attendee
10	Madile Ramos Lopes da Cruz Zego	Attendee

Table 2 : Webinar 2 Attendees

B1: ORION GDT Story Template

ORION : AugmentCity User Story Template

Use Case:

- Add use case name.

Title:

- A short, descriptive title for the story.
- Example: *Energy use visualisation...*

As a [role],

- This defines who the end user is.
- Example: *As an energy manager...*

I want to [action],

- This explains what the user wants to accomplish.
- Example: *I want to view real-time energy consumption data across different buildings...*

So that [benefit].

- This explains why the action is important, highlighting the business value or personal benefit.
- Example: *So that I can monitor and optimise energy usage in real-time to reduce costs and environmental impact.*

Acceptance Criteria (testable, specific, binary):

1. User can select individual buildings or view aggregated data for all buildings.
2. Energy consumption is displayed in a dynamic line chart showing real-time data updates.
3. The chart can toggle between different time intervals (e.g., hourly, daily, weekly).
4. The user can see a breakdown of energy consumption by source (e.g., electricity, gas, solar).
5. Alerts are generated if energy consumption exceeds a predefined threshold.
6. The visualisation includes tooltips to provide detailed data when hovering over points on the graph.

Additional Details (contextual, descriptive, optional):

- The chart should be interactive, allowing zooming and filtering by energy source.
- The data source must update every 5 minutes, ensuring real-time accuracy.
- Implementing colour-coded segments to indicate energy efficiency (green for optimal usage, red for excess consumption).

Figure 6 : GDT User Story Template

C1: ORION: Survey

Figure 7: Survey front cover

Figure 8: Example question from survey

C2: ORION: Survey Results

1 About You Section

1a Please identify yourself.

8 out of 8 people answered this question

1b Age

8 out of 8 people answered this question

1c Gender

8 out of 8 people answered this question

2 Previous Digital Twin Experience Section

2a Have you experienced or interacted with digital twins before?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

2b How would you rate your technical expertise in working with digital tools, software, and data?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

3 Did you attend the 1st ORION GDT Training webinar?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

4 Have you accessed and used the ORION Playground scene?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

5 Did you attend the 2nd ORION GDT Training webinar?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

6 Have you completed or been part of completing the GDT User Story for your Use Case?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

7 1st Webinar feedback

✓ 7a 1st WEBINAR: Did the presenter clearly explain the AugmentCity GDT tool ?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

✓ 7b 1st WEBINAR: Was the information presented at the 1st Webinar helpful to you in learning the AugmentCity GDT?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

7c 1st webinar topics covered:

8 out of 8 people answered this question

#1	Workspaces and scenes	#3.13 average
#2	Navigation	#4.25 average
#3	Adding Objects	#5.13 average
#4	Logging into Sandbox	#5.25 average
#5	Scenarios	#5.25 average
#6	Help pages	#5.75 average
#7	Opening a scene	#5.88 average
#8	Pin and comments tool	#7 average
#9	Weather settings	#7.63 average
#10	Terrain display themes	#8 average
#11	Terrain editing	#8.75 average

View details

8 Did you watch the training video that was released after the 1st GDT Webinar?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

9 Will you refer to the training video in the future?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

10 ORION Playground scene feedback

✓ 10d How useful is having access to the ORION Playground scene?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

☰ 11 2nd Webinar feedback

✓ 11a 2nd WEBINAR: Did the presenter clearly explain the different data types used in the AugmentCity GDT tool ?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

✓ 11b 2nd WEBINAR: Was the information presented at the 2nd Webinar helpful to you in learning the AugmentCity GDT?

8 out of 8 people answered this question

☰ 11c 2nd webinar topics covered:

8 out of 8 people answered this question

#1	Road networks (i.e.show traffic/ road capacity & movement)	#2.13 average
#2	Pins examples (locations of points of interest)	#3.13 average
#3	Bargraph timeline (Point data over time i.e. energy usage)	#3.13 average
#4	Heatmap timeline (area data over time ie microclimate changes)	#3.63 average
#5	Map overlays (colouring of the 3D model based on values)	#4.5 average
#6	Ribbons (showing linear data: i.e. energy grids)	#5.75 average
#7	Building colours (static): (identification of building types)	#6.38 average
#8	Building colours (timeline) : (i.e. building energy over time)	#8.13 average
#9	Lollipop : (KPI information for object or place)	#8.38 average
#10	3D objects : (importing of new 3d objects ie PV cells)	#9.88 average

∨ View details

12 Tick one circle per line to indicate how much you agree with the individual labels about the AugmentCity Graphical Digital Twin.

8 out of 8 people answered this question

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Easy to Learn	12.5%	12.5%	62.5%	12.5%	0%
Creative	12.5%	37.5%	50%	0%	0%
Fast	0%	25%	75%	0%	0%
Complicated	12.5%	12.5%	62.5%	12.5%	0%
Meets expectations	12.5%	37.5%	50%	0%	0%
Innovative	12.5%	37.5%	50%	0%	0%
Interesting	37.5%	12.5%	50%	0%	0%
Confusing	0%	0%	75%	25%	0%
Attractive	12.5%	25%	62.5%	0%	0%

13 After the training webinars and ORION playground scene, do you have a clearer understanding on how you may benefit from using the GDT?

4 out of 8 people answered this question

I will not be working directly with GDT but my impression is that the GDT is a very good tool to display different scenarios in an understandably way for people with little or no technical experience.

11 days ago

yes, it is very useful to know how GDT works

14 Do you anticipate potential gaps in services / simulations that the GDT can show?

2 out of 8 people answered this question

Not yet, because I'm still exploring GDT's potential.

14 days ago

I think so.

15 days ago